

Amperometric Determination of Copper and Silver with 1,5-bis(Benzylidene) Thiocarbohydrazone

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1,5-bis(Benzylidene) thiocarbohydrazone (BBTCH) is recommended as an amperometric reagent for copper(I) and silver(I). The organic chelating agent forms an orange precipitate with copper(I) and a yellow precipitate with silver(I) in the molar ratio 1 : 2 (ligand : metal) in the pH range 4.0-6. The lower limits of determination of copper(I) and silver(I) at a dropping mercury electrode are 0.04 mg in 6.29×10^{-5} M solution and 0.22 mg in 2.04×10^{-4} M solution, respectively. Copper can be amperometrically determined with BBTCH in presence of all other metal ions. The determination of silver is possible in presence of all other metal ions except gold(III) and mercury(II). The method has been successfully applied in the determination of copper and silver contents of a sample of silver coin. Furthermore, the amount of copper present in a brass sample has also been determined accurately by this method.

VARIOUS organic reagents containing different functional groups have been employed in the amperometric determination of copper¹⁻⁵. The procedures based on the use of these reagents are not satisfactory because of poor sensitivity or selectivity. Recently, thiosalicylamide⁶ has been employed as a sulphide precipitating agent for amperometric titration of the metal. The organic reagents proposed for the amperometry of silver are mostly thio-ligands⁷⁻¹². Amongst these, 8-mercaptoquinoline¹¹ and unithol¹² are found to be the effective titrants.

or any alkyl or aryl group) possessing both sulphur and nitrogen atoms available for coordination with the metal ions are likely to behave as versatile multidentate ligand like dithizone. The applications of this class of compounds have not been studied by analytical chemists so far. In our previous communication¹³ we have established the potentiality of 1,5-bis(benzylidene)-thiocarbohydrazone (BBTCH) as an effective reagent in the amperometric determination of lead. In the present study, BBTCH has been employed successfully in the amperometric titrations of copper and silver. The organic reagent produces a greenish complex with copper(II), which, however, has no definite composition. The reagent forms stable insoluble orange and yellow complexes with copper(I) and silver(I), respectively. The instantaneous and quantitative reaction of copper(I) and silver(I) with BBTCH at room temperature in the molar ratio 1 : 2 (ligand : metal) has been made the basis of the amperometric determination of these two metal ions.

Experimental

Preparation and properties of the chelating agent : 1,5-bis(benzylidene) thiocarbohydrazone was prepared according to Guha *et al.*¹⁴. To an aqueous hydrochloric acid solution of thiocarbohydrazide (containing minimum quantity of the acid) was added an alcoholic solution of benzaldehyde dropwise with constant shaking until the molar ratio of benzaldehyde just exceeded twice that of thiocarbohydrazide, when a yellow mass separated. The reaction mixture was warmed for about 15 min on a boiling water bath, filtered, washed with ethanol-water mixture. The crude product was crystallized from 80% acetic acid. A triple recrystallized sample was used in the amperometric titrations.

The reagent is insoluble in water, moderately soluble in ethanol and highly soluble in dimethylsulphoxide, dimethylformamide, etc. It is sufficiently stable towards heat and light, and melts at 194°. The compound is stable without any sign of decomposition for a pretty long time when stored in a desiccator.

Reagents and chemicals : A standard solution of the BBTCH was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity of the reagent in dimethylsulphoxide-ethanol (1 : 9) medium. The solution was stable for 2-3 days when stored in a refrigerator and could be used as a primary standard.

Standard solutions of copper(II) and silver(I) were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of copper sulphate or silver nitrate in double distilled water. The copper content was determined iodometrically and silver(I) content gravimetrically as silver chloride. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of their nitrates or

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sulphates in distilled water acidified with sulphuric acid.

The pH of the solutions was adjusted by adding 5% sodium acetate (for copper) or 5% sodium potassium tartrate (for silver) and 2.0 M sulphuric acid. For high pH values, solutions of 2 M ammonium hydroxide and 0.5 M ammonium nitrate were used.

0.05% solution of gelatin and 1.0 M solution of potassium nitrate were employed as maxima suppressor and supporting electrolyte, respectively for silver(I).

Apparatus: A pen recording polarograph (Radel Kis, Hungary, type OH 101/1) was used to obtain the polarogram of the reagent solution and a Toshniwal manual polarograph (Type CNOZA) along with a sensitive galvanometer was used for diffusion current measurements during titrations. A Systronics pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedures for amperometric titrations of copper and silver: For the amperometric titration of copper, an aliquot of copper sulphate solution was taken in the titration cell. Copper(II) was reduced to copper(I) by excess hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.0-6.0. The volume of the solution was made up to 10-15 ml with water and ethanol (addition of ethanol was necessary to avoid precipitation of the reagent). The titration medium contained 15% ethanol.

For the determination of silver, an aliquot of silver nitrate solution was taken in the titration cell followed by the addition of KNO_3 and gelatin solutions. The pH of the solutions were adjusted between 4.0 and 6.0. The final solution contained 0.1 M KNO_3 , 0.005% gelatin and 15% ethanol in a total volume of 10-15 ml.

Titration of both the metal ions were carried out in a simple cylindrical glass cell connected to an external saturated calomel electrode with an agar- KNO_3 salt bridge. The average drop-time of mercury was 3.6 sec at a height of 42 cm of the dropping mercury electrode. The metal solutions were deaerated by passing pure nitrogen for about 30 min and then titrated with the addition of a small amount of standard BBTCH solution at a time at an applied voltage of -0.5 volt (vs SCE). The solutions (copper or silver) were again bubbled for simultaneous deaeration and agitation for 1 min. An orange and a yellow precipitate separated in the case of copper and silver, respectively. The galvanometer reading was noted. Similar readings were taken corresponding to further progressive small additions of the reagent solution. As the reagent solution did not produce any wave upto a potential of -1.6 volt, a low constant current was obtained after the end point. The accurate end point was obtained from the respective L-shaped titration curve (Fig. 1) making allowances for the

necessary volume change during titrations. The metal ions (copper or silver) were estimated at the titration end point corresponding to stoichiometric composition of 1 : 2 (ligand : metal ratio).

Fig. 1.

In the interference studies, known amounts of foreign ions were added, pH adjusted between 4.0 and 5.0 and similar procedures were followed for the titrations of copper(I) and silver(I). The results are shown in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the optimum pH range for the amperometric determination of copper(I) and silver(I) lie between 4.0 to 6.0 and the reagent reacts with both the metal ions in the stoichiometric ratio 1 : 2 (ligand : metal). It is evident from Table 2 that 0.04 mg of copper (in a 6.29×10^{-5} M solution)

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COPPER AND SILVER WITH BBTCH

pH	Amount of metal mole $\times 10^{-6}$	Amount of reagent required mole $\times 10^{-6}$	Metal/ligand molar ratio
Copper			
3.1	15.95	9.0	1.77
3.7	15.95	8.15	1.96
4.0	15.95	7.96	2.01
4.8	15.95	8.0	1.99
5.5	15.95	7.97	2.00
6.0	15.95	7.96	2.00
7.4	15.95	8.15	1.96
10.4	15.95	9.86	1.61
Silver			
3.3	15.30	8.4	1.82
4.0	15.30	7.72	1.98
4.8	15.30	7.65	2.00
5.3	15.30	7.69	1.99
6.0	15.30	7.63	2.0
7.2	15.30	7.86	1.95
8.2	15.30	8.6	1.78

and 0.22 mg of silver (in a 2.04×10^{-4} M solution) respectively, can be measured accurately within a short time. Table 3 shows that copper(I) can be

TABLE 2—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COPPER AND SILVER WITH BBTCH

Amount taken mg	Amount found mg	Error mg
	Copper	
3.01	2.98	-0.03
2.01	1.99	-0.02
1.005	1.010	+0.005
0.62	0.61	-0.01
0.40	0.405	+0.005
0.20	0.205	+0.005
0.10	0.10	±0.00
0.08	0.08	±0.00
0.04	0.04	±0.00
	Silver	
3.29	3.31	+0.02
2.46	2.44	-0.02
1.65	1.65	±0.00
0.82	0.81	-0.01
0.49	0.48	-0.01
0.33	0.32	-0.01
0.22	0.22	±0.00

TABLE 3—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COPPER AND SILVER IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Foreign ion added	Determination of copper (Copper taken=1.20 mg)			Determination of silver (Silver taken=1.65 mg)		
	Amount of foreign ion added mg	Amount of Cu found mg	Error mg	Amount of foreign ion added mg	Amount of Ag found mg	Error mg
Tartrate	100	1.20	±0.00	200	1.65	±0.00
Citrate	50	1.20	±0.00	50	1.64	-0.01
Fluoride	35	1.21	+0.01	—	—	—
EDTA	—	—	—	25	1.66	+0.01
Ni(II)	10	1.22	+0.02	10	1.65	±0.00
Zn(II)	20	1.22	+0.02	20	1.66	+0.01
Pb(II)	10	1.21	+0.01	10	1.66	+0.01
Cd(II)	10	1.21	+0.01	20	1.66	+0.01
Co(II)	10	1.22	+0.02	10	1.65	±0.00
Mn(II)	20	1.21	+0.01	10	1.64	-0.01
Fe(III)	10	1.21	+0.01	5	1.63	-0.02
Tl(I)	20	1.21	+0.01	10	1.64	-0.01
Sb(II)	10	1.20	±0.00	—	—	—
Sb(III)	10	1.19	-0.01	10	1.64	0.01
As(III)	10	1.20	±0.00	10	1.64	-0.01
Bi(III)	2	1.22	+0.02	2	1.66	+0.01
Ag(I)	2	1.19	-0.01	—	—	—
Ag(II)	2	1.21	+0.01	—	—	—
Au(III)	2	1.21	+0.01	—	—	—
Cu(II)	—	—	—	2	1.65	±0.00
Al(III)	10	1.20	±0.00	2	1.63	-0.00

determined in the presence of appreciable amounts of all the associated metal ions. Interference of nickel(II), zinc(II), lead(II), cadmium(II), cobalt(II), iron(III), manganese(II), tin(II), arsenic(III) and antimony(III) in the determination of copper(I) is avoided by tartrate and that of bismuth(III) by citric acid. Cyanide and EDTA however, interfere in the determination of copper. Silver can be determined in the presence of all the associated metal ions except mercury(II) and gold(III). The interference of copper(II) and bismuth(III) in the determination of silver(I) can be avoided by adding

EDTA. Cyanide and anions such as halides, phosphate, oxalate which yield insoluble compound with silver(I) should be avoided.

Most of the organic reagents employed so far in the amperometric determination of copper(I) and silver(I) suffer serious interference from the associated metal ions. The advantage of the use of BBTCH for the purpose lies in the fact that it permits determination of copper(I) and silver(I) in the presence of almost all the associated metal ions. Furthermore, the sensitivity of the method is quite high so that even 0.04 mg of copper and 0.22 mg of silver can be determined rapidly with high accuracy. The reagent is stable and can be used as a primary standard.

Accuracy and precision: The relative mean error and the coefficient of variations were calculated from a set of five experiments under identical conditions. The values were found to be 0.31% and 0.54% respectively for 1.005 mg of copper(I) and 0.32% and 0.85% respectively for 1.645 mg of silver(I).

Analyses of technical material :

A. Determination of copper and silver in a silver coin : A weighed quantity of the coin in the form of a thin sheet was digested with minimum amount of 1 : 1 nitric acid, filtered and diluted to the mark in a volumetric flask.

Silver : An aliquot of the solution was taken, pH adjusted to about 5.0 and titration of silver was carried out in the presence of EDTA by the recommended method.

Silver estimated	
BBTCH method	91.6%
Chloride method	91.2%

Copper : An aliquot of the coin solution was taken and most of the silver(I) present was separated as silver chloride. Copper(II) was reduced to copper(I) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The pH of the solution was adjusted to about 5.0. Titration was carried out in presence of tartrate following the recommended procedure.

Copper estimated	
BBTCH method	7.9%
Iodometry	7.8%

B. Determination of copper in a sample of brass : A weighed quantity of a brass sample was digested with 1 : 1 nitric acid. Oxides of nitrogen were removed by repeated evaporation with conc. sulphuric acid. The solution was filtered and diluted to a measured volume. An aliquot of this solution was taken, followed by the reduction of copper(II) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The pH was adjusted to 4.0-5.0. Tartrate was added and the titration carried out following the recommended procedure. The results were verified by a standard method.

Copper estimated	
BBTCH method	57.9%
Iodometric method	57.5%

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